

Complexometric determination of mercury(II) and thallium(III) using cysteamine hydrochloride as releasing agent

Abraham Joseph^a, B. Narayana^{*b} and K. Subrahmanya Bhat^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, St. Pius X. College, Rajapuram, Kasaragod-571 532, India

^bDepartment of Studies in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199, India

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A simple complexometric method is described for the determination of mercury(II) and thallium(III) using cysteamine hydrochloride as a selective releasing agent. Hg^{II} or Tl^{III} solution with diverse ions are initially complexed with a known excess of EDTA, the excess EDTA is then back-titrated with lead nitrate solution at pH 5.0–6.0 (hexamine) using xylenol orange as indicator. A slight excess of the releasing agent is then added and the EDTA released from the metal-EDTA complex is quantitatively determined as above. Both the determinations work well at low and high concentrations of metal ions (4–125 mg of Hg^{II} and 5–108 mg Tl^{III}) with a permissible relative error of $\pm 0.4\%$ and standard deviation ≤ 0.04 mg. The validity of the method is confirmed by extending it to the determination of Hg^{II} and Tl^{III} in several synthetic binary mixtures.

Mercury and thallium are usually determined by complexation with EDTA followed by selective decomposition of the metal-EDTA complex with a suitable masking agent. Based on the principle of masking and demasking, several attempts have been made to find out a highly suitable reagent for these metal ions, but none of these methods^{1–3} satisfies all the requirements. Some of the limitations of these reagents can be easily overcome by the use of cysteamine hydrochloride.

Results and Discussion

The Hg^{II} ion forms a highly stable complex with easily polarizable ligands containing S or N donor atoms. Cysteamine hydrochloride being a potential complexing agent releases EDTA from the Hg-EDTA complex (the complex is less stable, $\log \beta = 15.3$). Experimental results show that the release of EDTA is quantitative and reproducible.

Thallium forms a stable complex with EDTA only in the +3 state⁴ and shows little tendency towards +1 state. Even if Tl^I forms a complex with EDTA, it may do so only under higher pH (8.0–9.0) condition. But the decomposition of this complex takes place at lower pH. This redox behaviour of Tl^I–Tl^{III} can be successfully employed for the complexometric determination of thallium. Cysteamine hydrochloride, a reducing as well as a complexing agent converts Tl^{III} to Tl^I and releases the previously complexed EDTA from Tl^{III}-EDTA complex. The presence of Tl^I in the reaction mixture is confirmed by spot-test⁵. Absence of any precipitate or any unwanted colour in the reaction mixture during titration favours a sharp end-point.

Accurate and reproducible results have been obtained with an acceptable relative error of $\pm 0.4\%$ and standard deviation ≤ 0.04 mg. A large excess of the reagent has no adverse effects in both the cases.

The effect of different metal ions including rare earth ions and anions on the quantitative determination of Hg^{II} and Tl^{III} were studied using solution containing 12.09 mg of Hg^{II} or 15.74 mg of Tl^{III}. The tolerance limit (mg in parenthesis) for the cations are as follows: Zn^{II} (100); Mn^{II} (10); Ni^{II} (50); Cd^{II} (60); Co^{II} (5); Al^{III}, Pt^{IV} (25); Fe^{III}, Cr^{III},

Table 1 Analysis of synthetic binary mixtures*

Mixture (Composition)	Hg/Tl Found	S D	Recovery %
Mercury			
Hg + Zn (42 + 58)	41.84	0.03	99.62
Hg + Na (67 + 33)	67.13	0.04	100.19
Hg + Mg (50 + 50)	49.96	0.03	99.92
Hg + Sn (50 + 50) ^a	49.93	0.03	99.86
Thallium			
Tl + Ti (20 + 80)	19.82	0.04	99.10
Tl + Zr (50 + 50)	49.72	0.03	99.41
Tl + Pd (50 + 50) ^a	49.78	0.03	99.90
Tl + Bi (75 + 25)	75.31	0.03	100.40

*Average of five determinations ^aMasked by secondary agents

Au^{III} (10); Ce^{III}, Ru^{III}, V^{IV}, Ti^{IV} (20); Rh^{III}, U^{VI} (30). But severe interference was noticed in the case of Cu^{II}, Pd^{II} and Sn^{IV}. However, the interference can be eliminated by the use of proper masking agents such as 5% solution of ammo-

nium fluoride for Sn^{IV} , 10% solution of thioglycolic acid for Cu^{II} and a 1% solution of DL-methionine for Pd^{II} . The interference of Tl^{III} in the determination of Hg^{II} can be eliminated by 5% solution of ascorbic acid² and that of Hg^{II} in the determination of Tl^{III} can be eliminated by 10% solution of acetyl acetone³. Larger concentration of Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} and Au^{III} make some trouble in the end-point detection (>10 mg). Anions like borate, sulphate, chloride, acetate, tartrate, fluoride and oxalate are tolerated up to 200 mg.

Various synthetic mixtures of mercury or thallium with other metal ions corresponding to the alloy compositions were analysed for the metal ion quantitatively using cysteamine hydrochloride. Fairly good values were obtained for Hg^{II} or Tl^{III} (Table 1).

Experimental

All reagents were of A.R. grade. Mercury(II) nitrate solution (0.04 M) was standardised by thionalide method⁸. Thallium(III) standard solution was prepared using thallos nitrate⁹. Lead nitrate solution (0.04 M) was prepared in double-distilled water and standardised⁸. EDTA solution (0.04 M) was prepared in double-distilled water. A 1% aqueous solution of cysteamine hydrochloride was used.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the solution (containing 4.0–125 mg of Hg^{II} or 5.0–108 mg of Tl^{III}), an excess of 0.04 M EDTA solution was added, diluted to about 70 ml and the pH adjusted to 5.0–6.0 with hexamine (10 ± 4 g). The surplus EDTA was then titrated with lead nitrate solution using xylenol orange as indicator. Aqueous cysteamine hydrochloride solution was then added in excess (1 ml for every 5 mg of Hg^{II} or 2 ml for every 9 mg of Tl^{III}) and titrated immediately against lead nitrate solution as before. The second titration volume corresponds to the amount of

EDTA released from the metal-EDTA complex which is equivalent to the amount of Hg^{II} or Tl^{III} present.

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